

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE INGENIERÍA
AGRONÓMICA, ALIMENTARIA Y DE BIOSISTEMAS

MASTER IN COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY

**GENERATION OF A SPANISH
ANNOTATED CORPUS WITH
BIOMEDICAL ENTITIES**

MASTER'S THESIS

Abstract: 278 words

Manuscript: 7538 words

Author: Lucía Sánchez González

Tutors: Carlos Badenes Olmedo and María Poveda Villalón

Institution: Ontology Engineering Group, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Table of content

1. Acknowledgments	2
2. Abstract	3
3. Introduction	3
3.1. Overview	3
3.2. Objectives	6
4. Materials and Methods	6
4.1. Systematic Review of English and Spanish Biomedical Corpora	6
4.2. Establishment of a workflow for the annotation of the corpus	10
4.3. Spanish Biomedical Corpus	14
4.4. Evaluation of the annotations	15
4.5. Publication of the annotations	16
5. Results	17
5.1. Systematic Review: English and Spanish Biomedical Corpora	17
5.2. Spanish Biomedical Corpus	21
5.3. Evaluation of the annotations	23
6. Discussion	25
7. Conclusions	28
8. References	29

1. Acknowledgments

I want to give my most sincere thanks to Carlos Badenes Olmedo and María Poveda Villalón for giving me the opportunity to carry out this project and for having guided me with the greatest patience and motivation throughout its course. I also want to thank the members of the Ontology Engineering Group where I have learned and enjoyed enormously. To my family and friends for being an indispensable support day after day. And finally, to show my gratitude to the project DRUGS4COVID++: Servicios de Inteligencia Artificial para la creación de un grafo de conocimientos sobre fármacos usados en el control clínico de la enfermedad, a partir de la explotación de grandes corpus de documentación científica sobre SARS-COV-2 y COVID-19-AYUDAS FUNDACIÓN BBVA A EQUIPOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CIENTÍFICA SARS-CoV-2 y COVID-19.

2. Abstract

The great advances in the technological world have led to an exponential increase in the data and information produced, especially in Biomedicine. However, the format in which this knowledge is structured is highly heterogeneous and, in the worst-case scenario, non-machine readable. Consequently, it is more difficult for biomedical professionals to access it. The field of Natural Language Processing provides models/tools that extract the information and transform it in a format that is machine-readable so the retrieval and access to the knowledge can be automated and easy. To carry out this information extraction task, these models need to be provided with data already structured to employ them as a reference, such as an annotated corpus. However, most of the biomedical annotated corpus are in English and therefore there is a lack of these kinds of NLP resources in other languages such as Spanish. In addition, there is also a large percentage of corpus that is not openly available, which further hinders its usage to create more resources in NLP.

That is why this project aims to annotate a Spanish corpus with biomedical entities and with semantic relationships and publish it openly. Firstly, we performed a systematic literature review of English and Spanish corpora annotated with biomedical entities with the purpose of identifying which is the methodology and format employed by most of the researchers to perform that task. Then we designed a work environment to annotate a Spanish corpus with eleven types of biomedical entities and eighth types of semantic relations. Finally, we have carried out a preliminary annotation to a set of 18 clinical cases resulting in a Spanish corpus with 324 biomedical entities and 170 semantic relations.

3. Introduction

3.1. Overview

The amount of information published in biomedicine increases exponentially every day. Thanks to the great advance in the field of informatics, it is increasingly easy to access this information through computers, but difficult for experts to keep up to date. A large proportion of data is published in an unstructured format, which implies that medical professionals and

researchers have to carry out numerous searches and exhaustive readings in order to find the information that they need. A way to do this is manually, which reduces the knowledge acquired, since it is hard for humans to handle that information overload. **Natural Language Processing (NLP)** acquires a main role in creating models and sophisticated tools that facilitate the extraction of information (1). NLP is an area of Artificial Intelligence which provides computers the ability to understand text and spoken words written by humans. A field of NLP is the Information Extraction (IE), where knowledge is extracted from texts, and it is transformed into a structured format (for example XML) that machines can read (2). This can be applied to multiple areas of biomedicine. For example, Haerian, K. et al designed a method (3) that differentiate cases in which cases the patient's disease is responsible for the adverse events rather than a drug by using IE in electronic health records.

There is a class of IE models and tools that belong to the Machine Learning Supervised area that, to carry out their extraction tasks, they first need to learn from already structured data to use as a reference. One example of this structured data is the annotated corpus. A **corpus** (plural, corpora) is a linguistic resource consisting of a collection of texts that are machine readable. An **annotated corpus** is a corpus to which additional linguistic information has been added. There are numerous types of annotations that can be provided, for example the Part-Of-Speech (POS) annotations in which words are tagged indicating to what class of word they belong (noun, adjective, pronoun, etc.). Other examples of annotations are the phonetic ones, in which information about the pronunciation of the words is added, or the **semantic annotations** where information about the meaning of the terms is provided (4). Annotated corpus can be also classified as “Gold Standard Corpus” (GSC) or as “Silver Standard Corpus” (SSC). The main difference between them is that the whole process of annotation and analysis of those annotations in the GSC are made manually by the annotators, whereas in the SSC this whole process is automated by machine. While SSC had the advantage to reduce the time and effort costs, GSC are more known to store annotations of better quality to train machine learning models.

Our work is focused on creating a Spanish Gold Standard corpus annotated with semantic entities and relations belonging to the biomedical domain. A semantic entity is a word or groups of words that have a meaning attached; for example, *Rabies*, is a semantic entity of the type Viral Disease. A semantic relation is a relation between two or more entities based on their meaning; for example, the entities *Aspirin* and *Headache* have the semantic relation

“Relieves”. In the literature there are a large amount of English annotated corpus with biomedical entities and relations, such as the GENIA corpus (5) which contains 1,999 MEDLINE abstracts, CLEF (6) corpus composed by 20,000 cancer patient records, or NCBI disease corpus (7) which contains 793 PubMed abstracts annotated. All these three corpora are Gold Standard but only GENIA and CLEF contain annotated semantic relations apart from medical entities.

As mentioned before, there are plenty of these kinds of corpora in the state of art, however there are still some open issues in this area. Most of the corpora described are in the English language (8). Since English is the predominant language for the publication of documentation and reports resulting from research, a large proportion of the advances produced in NLP have been oriented towards this language. Consequently, there is a large amount of biomedical content in other languages that is not used and, therefore, it becomes more difficult to access this knowledge. Regarding the Spanish language, although the number of corpora described is still very small compared to the English one, there are more professionals involved in the creation of this type of linguistic resources in this language.

Another open issue regarding annotated corpora is the lack of availability and reuse of them. Despite the large number of articles in the literature that describe the creation of a corpus, it is quite common that the authors either do not openly publish the annotations created or have them published on their personal or institutional web page, which eventually has stopped working. Additionally, this does not apply only to the annotations, but it is also common that the tools and resources created and used by the authors are private and not available. All this creates an enormous gap in the transference of knowledge and information in research science.

Regarding the biomedical corpus annotated in Spanish, we found that there are two main shortcomings: The first is that a large proportion of the corpus described do not contain annotated semantic relations, such as the CT-EBM-SP corpus (9), or contain only one or two types of these such the IxaMed-GS(10). Secondly, as mentioned in the previous paragraph, we also found lack of availability in the Spanish biomedical corpora. Either the authors do not indicate where is possible to download or look at their annotations (11) or they indicate that to obtain the corpus you have to go through an application process due to confidentiality issues (10). Therefore, with this project we aim to annotate a Spanish corpus with biomedical

entities with their possible semantic relations and publish it openly in order to promote open and accessible science.

3.2. Objectives

To address these problems, this work designs a workflow to annotate a Spanish corpus with biomedical entities and semantic relations. In addition, all the tools and data that have been employed are freely available with the purpose to contribute to the open and reproducible. To do so, there were established three main goals:

1° Goal: To identify what are the main characteristics of this type of corpus, we seek to perform a systematic review of the literature on Spanish and English corpora annotated with biomedical entities (drugs, diseases, symptoms, genes, etc.) and semantic relations (interaction, treatment, replacement, etc.).

2° Goal: Define an environmental work that allows to annotate biomedical entities and their semantic relations. To achieve this goal, a workflow is prepared based on the information collected in the 1° Goal. It must indicate the possible sources where to obtain the information that the corpus will contain, the NLP tools considered optimal to carry out the annotation task, and the formats to be used for annotations and publication of the corpus.

3° Goal: Creation and publication of a preliminary version of a Spanish annotated corpus following the standards identified in the 1° Goal and employing the environmental work designed in the 2° Goal. Once built, its quality will be measured, and it will be published with an open license in a repository that promotes open science such as Zenodo.

4. Materials and Methods

All the scripts employed in this project can be found in the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/LuciaSG99/BioEsCorpus.git>

4.1. Systematic Review of English and Spanish Biomedical Corpora

With the purpose to know what is the state of art of corpus annotated with biomedical entities, a search was carried out for systematic reviews in annotated corpora in biomedicine

in Spanish and English. However, there were found only two surveys (13,14) which are from a few years ago, 2014 and 2005 respectively, and therefore they are probably outdated. Then it was decided to carry out our own systematic review (12) to identify which tools, sources and formats are employed the most by the scientific community. In **Figure 1** are represented all the steps from this process.

Figure 1. Schema of the systematic review process. Thick arrows represent the output files from each step. Steps are represented inside boxes with curved corners

4.1.1. Search in bibliographic databases

To identify Spanish and English biomedical corpora, the search was applied in three bibliographic databases: **Web of Science (WoS)** (15), **Scopus** (16) and **Pubmed** (17). On one

hand, WoS and Scopus are paid-access platforms which contain a high number of scientific articles belonging to a wide range of research areas. On the other hand, Pubmed is a free resource focused on the retrieval of biomedical and life sciences literature. These three databases allow you to perform a query and to download in a file the metadata of all the results from those queries. For each database, there were two queries, one to search for English corpora and another to search for the Spanish ones. All search queries are represented in **Table 1**. The search for the key words “*Biomedical corpus*”, for English corpora, or “*Spanish Biomedical corpus*” for Spanish corpora, was filtered by looking at the title and abstract of the articles. Also, it was established to search only for those articles that contained an abstract.

Table 1. Representation of the queries employed to search for English and Spanish biomedical corpora in Web of Science, Scopus and Pubmed.

Database	English query	Spanish query
Web of Science	(TI=(Biomedical corpus)) OR AB=(Biomedical corpus)	(TI=(Spanish Biomedical corpus)) OR AB=(Spanish Biomedical corpus)
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (biomedical AND corpus)	TITLE-ABS-KEY (spanish AND biomedical AND corpus)
Pubmed	("biomedical"[Title/Abstract] AND "corpus"[Title/Abstract]) AND ((fha[Filter]) AND (fft[Filter]))	("spanish"[Title/Abstract] AND "biomedical"[Title/Abstract] AND "corpus"[Title/Abstract]) AND ((fha[Filter]) AND (fft[Filter]))

Once the query was performed, all the metadata (authors, title, publication date, DOI, abstract, etc.) from the articles retrieved from Scopus and WoS were downloaded in a CSV file. In the case of Pubmed the metadata was saved in a text file (.txt) in the format “Pubmed” in which the metadata is printed by rows instead of columns. In order to have all the data in the same format, a script in R was created in order to transform the metadata of the Pubmed

text file into a csv file. Finally, six datasets of metadata of articles were obtained (two per database, an English and a Spanish dataset).

4.1.2. Inclusion and Exclusion filtering

The next step consisted in filtering each dataset of articles. There were applied one inclusion criteria and one exclusion criteria:

- **Inclusion criteria:** Keep only those articles which contain the words “biomedical” OR “clinical” OR “medical” OR “bio” OR “biomedicine” AND “corpus” in their titles.
- **Exclusion criteria:** Dismiss those that did not have a DOI code.

Then, we identified if there were duplicate articles between the datasets of the databases using their DOI code. A final csv file containing all the articles that met those criteria was obtained.

4.1.3. Manual Revision

A second and manual filtering was performed to obtain a final set of articles. There were established the three following questions as inclusion criteria:

- 1) Is the final output of the project an annotated corpus?
- 2) Is the corpus' language English or Spanish?
- 3) Does the corpus' content belong to the biomedical domain?

The abstract of each article was read in order to answer those questions. Only the articles that accomplished these criteria were stored as a final dataset. This step was performed both for English and Spanish articles.

4.1.4. Feature selection

Once the final lists of articles were obtained, the next step was to read each paper and identify a series of features that all those projects could have in common and could allow to answer scientific questions. The most relevant characteristics identified in the articles are:

- 1) **Article Information:** Metadata from the article such as Authors, DOI, Year of Publication, Source of publication, the Article's availability, etc.

- 2) **Corpus Information:** Information about the final output of the corpus such as its size, the types of entities it contains, its language, etc.
- 3) **Creation process:** The process the authors followed to construct the corpus. For example: number of annotators, type of annotation tool used, the metric employed to measure the corpus' annotations quality, etc.
- 4) **Availability:** If the data, code, and resources employed to create the corpus are available.

The result of the systematic review is a table containing the results for each article for each feature described (see [Supplementary Material](#)).

4.2. Establishment of a workflow for the annotation of the corpus

In this step, the establishment of a workflow was carried out in which it was chosen which data, tools and output would be used to create the corpus.

4.2.1. Input dataset

To facilitate the annotation process, a search for an already created Spanish corpus which contained biomedical text was performed. The criteria for the search of the corpus were:

- 1) It had to be in Spanish.
- 2) It must not have any kind of annotation.
- 3) It must be freely available with an open and permissive licence.

Finally, it was decided to employ the **Spanish Clinical Case Corpus (SPACCC)** ([18](#)) which contains 1,000 clinical reports in Spanish from the resource SciELO. The corpus is published in Zenodo ([15](#)) with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence in a text file (.txt) format. This resource belongs to the project “Plan de Impulso de las Tecnologías del Lenguaje de la Agenda Digital (Plan TL)” from the Spanish government.

4.2.2. Annotator

The annotator is the person who carries out the identification of entities and relationships in the texts. We decided to look for people who had a biomedical profile, who had knowledge

about the type of entities we wanted to record. Additionally, we saw that, in the corpora from the systematic review, the average number of annotators employed was three. Using a large number of annotators may mean that there is a lower degree of agreement between them and using one or two annotators would mean that the annotations are biased towards their criteria. That is why we say that three was the optimal number of annotators.

4.2.3. Annotation Tool

For the annotation tool, we were looking for a tool that would be easy to use, and that allowed not only to annotated entities but also to annotated semantic relations between them. It should also have an open and permissive licence. From the systematic review it was identified that the tool that is employed the most by the researchers is **brat Annotation Tool** (19) that allows to annotate relations and entities. However, its web server is not available online, and some troubles arose when trying to install it locally, so we had to dismiss it as an option.

Finally, we decided to use **Text Annotation Editor (TextAE)** (20), which is a web-based, integrated visual text annotation editor. This tool has different modes that allow us to annotate entities and semantic relationships very easily. It has a MIT licence, so it is open and free to use and modify. In addition, we also found that TextAE could be adapted to our task since it can be embedded in an HTML document and since the authors published on GitHub some templates to use.

4.2.4. Annotation Guideline and Tool Usage Guide

To provide instructions to the annotators on what were the entities and relations they had to annotate in the texts, an **annotation guideline** was created. It is divided in the following sections:

D) Groups of entities: There were established **eight biomedical entities** and **three linguistic entities** to annotate. For each entity there is a definition for the kind of terms that belong to that label and at least three examples of those terms. The biomedical entities that the corpus supposed to contain were: *Gen* (Gene), *Proteína* (Protein), *Glúcido* (Carbohydrate), *Enfermedad* (Disease), *Signo* (Clinic Sign), *Síntoma* (Symptom), *Medicamento* (Drug), *Sigla* (Acronym), *Abreviatura* (Abbreviation), *Alias* (Alias).

Since the input files are clinical reports, the groups of medical entities (*Enfermedad*, *Signo*, *Síntoma* and *Medicamento*) were essential to be annotated. However, we also wanted to label the molecular ones (*Gen*, *Proteína*, *Lípido* and *Glúcido*) because there are not too many Spanish corpus that contain those kinds of entities. Due to the tendency in the medical domain to use abbreviations and acronyms (21) we also included those entities (*Sigla*, *Abreviatura* and *Alias*).

II) Semantic relations: There are **eight semantic relations** represented in the guideline. For each relation it is indicated what are the entities that could to be annotated as the subject of the relation and what are the entities which should be annotated as the object. These relations are represented in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Representation of the eight semantic relations indicated to the annotators. 1° Column represents the predicate of that relation, between brackets there is its English translation; 2° column represents the type of entities which can act as subject of the relation; 3° column the possible object entities.

Predicate	Subject	Object
Implicado en (Involved in)	Proteína/Lípido/Glúcido/Medicamento	Enfermedad
Activa (Activates)	Proteína/Lípido/Glúcido/Medicamento	Proteína/Gen
Inhibe (Inhibits)	Proteína/Lípido/Glúcido/Medicamento	Proteína/Gen
Interacciona con (Interacts with)	Proteína/Lípido/Glúcido/Medicamento	Proteína/Gen/Lípido/ Glúcido/Medicamento
Alivia (Alleviates)	Medicamento	Signo/Síntoma
Cura (Treats)	Medicamento	Enfermedad

Previene (Prevents)	Medicamento	Enfermedad
Refiere a (Refers to)	Siglas/Abreviatura/Alias	Entidad

To design these relationships, we based on the semantic relationships of the UMLS semantic network (22).

III) Annotation Criteria: A list of linguistics rules to guide the annotators were created to obtain more homogenous annotations. Some of these are:

- *Annotation object:* Only those words or groups of words that form nominal groups should be annotated.
- *Numbers:* Only in the case of entities containing numbers in their nominal group, these lasts will be annotated together with the rest of the words, but just when it is essential to identify and understand that biomedical term. Regarding entities such as “Treatment” or “Drugs”, numerical terms corresponding to doses or concentrations usually appear next to them; these should not be labelled.
- *Non-Spanish terms:* Those terms from other languages that the annotator considers to be included in one of the groups of entities and that are in common use in the biomedical field will also be annotated. For example, in “Enfermedad de Crohn”, the word “Crohn” should be annotated next to “Enfermedad de”.

IV) Resources: A list of biomedical vocabularies and terminologies available online are given. Annotators could use these resources if they came across unfamiliar terms or doubt the relationship between some entities. Some of the resources given were the *Diccionario de términos médicos de la Real Academia Nacional de Medicina de España* (23) or *Vocabulario Científico y Técnico de la Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales* (24).

Secondly, a guide for the use of the TextAE tool was designed. Within it there are demonstrations in which it is described step by step how to annotate the entities and the semantic relations with this tool and how to download the annotations once they are done.

4.3. Spanish Biomedical Corpus

Once the resources were identified and prepared, we proceeded to the creation of the gold standard corpus. We initially created a preliminary version of the corpus using eighteen clinical reports, annotated by three annotators, all of them with a molecular biology background, to validate our approach.

4.3.1. Adaptation of TextAE tool

In order to provide the annotators all the necessary resources without them having to do anything more than annotate, we modified the source code of TextAE to obtain the HTML files with the tool already including the text of the clinical reports. Therefore, each annotator was given eighteen HTML files containing the clinical report already inside TextAE (see an example of that HTML in **Figure 2**). In addition, each HTML had inside the tool all entity types and relations we had already defined, so the annotators hadn't had to create them themselves. They only had to select them when they would identify a biomedical term.

Figure 2. Example of a HTML file containing the TextAE tool with the text of a clinical report and with the entity menu displayed.

These files were sent to each annotator next to the annotation guide, the tool usage guide and, next to a text file in which annotators could write any comment or question they had during the annotation process.

4.3.2. Annotations Format

The final format decided to use for the publication of the annotations was the **brat format** as in the systematic review we saw that was the most frequent format used and it is easy to transform into. An example of an annotation in brat format is represented in **Figure 3**.

T6	Enfermedad 573 598	Diabetes Mellitus tipo II
T7	Enfermedad 600 627	Miocardiópatía hipertrófica

Figure 3. Representation of the brat format. It is a Tab-Separated Values (TSV) file in which: 1° Column represents an index indicating the annotation order (T6 would be the sixth term annotated), 2° column is the label associated to that term, 3° column is the offset of the term inside the text and the 4th column is the term itself.

The TextAE provides the annotations in the PubAnnotations format. It is a JSON file which stores the labels, terms, and relations next to their indexing information in the text. A script in Python was created to transform the PubAnnotations into the brat format.

4.4. Evaluation of the annotations

To measure the quality of the annotations the **Fleiss' Kappa (κ)** (25) value was calculated for both entities and semantic relations. It is an Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA) metric which allows us to measure the level of agreement between the annotators on labelling the terms into a given group of entities. This metric does not specify if the annotations are correct or not, but instead it indicates how reliable they are. It is used when the number of annotators is higher than two.

The formulate of Fleiss' Kappa is the following:

$$\kappa = \frac{P_o - P_e}{1 - P_e}$$

Where P_o stands for the observed probability of agreement between the annotators and P_e stands for the expected probability of agreement if the annotators label the words completely randomly. This metric takes values between -1 and 1. If the annotators completely agree then $\kappa = 1$, but if there is no agreement (other than what would be expected by chance) then $\kappa \leq 0$.

For each clinical report, the next approach was performed to calculate the Fleiss' Kappa value:

1° Create a **contingency table** in which the rows' names are all the entities labelled from all the annotators, the columns are the labels and inside the cells are the number of annotators that tagged that term with that label or relation. In the case of the semantic relations, the row's names were the subject and object term united by a “_”, for example: “*A.I.N.E._lesión inflamatoria*”, being “*A.I.N.E.*” the subject term and “*lesión inflamatoria*” the object.

To apply the Fleiss' Kappa equation, it is supposed that all the annotators have labelled the exact terms, but this was not our case since we directly gave the whole text to them without determining which were the entities they had to label. To correct this, we decided to establish that all the terms that the annotators had annotated were valid, and also to create a new class of label called “*NULL*”. Then in the case that, for example annotators A and B had annotated “*Diabetes*” as “*Enfermedad*”, but annotator C hadn't annotated that term at all, in the contingency table the row “*Diabetes*” could have the value of 2 in the “*Enfermedad*” column and a value of 1 in the column *NULL*.

2° Applied the Fleiss' Kappa equation to the contingency table using the function “Fleiss Kappa” from the Python module *statsmodels.stats.inter_rater* (26).

Once this metric was computed for the eighteen files, the median of them was calculated to obtain a unique metric for the whole corpus.

4.5. Publication of the annotations

Since we wanted our annotations of the corpus to be open and reusable for other people, we decided to publish all the resources and annotations from the corpus in Zenodo (27). This is an open repository which allows researchers to deposit research papers, datasets, softwares or reports. For each element submitted Zenodo provides a persistent digital object identifier (DOI), which makes the stored items easily citable. The publication in this repository allows this created dataset to be closer to achieve the FAIR principles that stand for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse (28). These principles describe how data should be organised to be more easily accessed, understood, exchanged, and reused. The principle of Findability establishes that the data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. By publishing our dataset in Zenodo, a wide world known open repository, and assigning them a DOI, we provide a unique identification to our annotations. Therefore, both machines

and humans can easily find it. Additionally, it also allows us to accomplish the principle of Accessibility, which stands that the data should be retrieved through a standardised communication protocol and be accessible even when the original resource is no longer accessible. The data can be retrieved by the public REST API of Zenodo and also Zenodo assured that the data will be retained for the lifetime of the repository that is 20 years at least.

5. Results

5.1. Systematic Review: English and Spanish Biomedical Corpora

5.1.1. Search in bibliographic databases

In *Table 3* are represented the number of articles retrieved per database and per corpus language. From these results we can notice that the number of articles retrieved specifying the language of the corpora is much smaller than the ones without mentioning a language. These values may be because: 1) The number of English corpora, as it was mentioned in the introduction section, is much bigger than the number of corpora in other languages; 2) By using the English query in which not language is mentioned, we probably had retrieved corpora in other languages.

Table 3. Number of articles retrieved by the queries in each database for English and Spanish biomedical corpora

Database	N° articles of English corpus	N° articles of Spanish corpus
Web of Science	1479	49
Scopus	2565	92
Pubmed	2495	19
Total	6539	160

5.1.2. First filtering

In this step was performed the filtering by the key words such as “biomedicine” and “corpus” in their titles and by dismissing those articles that did not have a DOI. Additionally, when

looking for duplicates in the English dataset, we saw that Pubmed and Scopus had 31 articles in common, Scopus and WoS had 41, and WoS and Pubmed had 3 in common. For the Spanish dataset we found that there were duplicated 3 articles between Scopus and WoS and 2 between Pubmed and Scopus. Removing the duplicates, we ended up with **85 articles** from the English dataset and **8 articles** from the Spanish dataset.

5.1.3. Second filtering

In this step each dataset of articles was filtered by looking if the output of the article was an annotated corpus, if it was either in English or Spanish, and belonged to the biomedical field. In the case of the Spanish dataset, only two of the articles accomplished the criteria and these papers were also in the English dataset. Because of this, we decided to have only one final dataset (resulting from filtering the English one), which consisted of **10 final articles**.

5.1.4. Identification of comparison features

After analysing all the articles from the final dataset, there were identified **28 total comparison features**, divided into the four sections mentioned before. The results of analysing the features identified in each section are shown below:

1. Article Information

All the articles from the final dataset were published as open access in journals with a Q1 or Q2 ranking, with *BMC Bioinformatics* being the most frequent. Out of 10, 5 articles were published after 2017, and the rest before 2016 being the oldest one from 2007.

2. Corpus Information

Among the 10 corpora, 9 of them are monolingual, being English the language of 8 of those 9 and only 1 in Spanish. There is one Multilingual, containing terms in English, French, German, Spanish, and Dutch.

For the type of entities those corpora contain, we looked for *Proteins*, *Genes*, *Diseases* and *Drugs entities*. Only one corpus contains all those groups of entities. Out of the 10 corpora, 8 annotated *Diseases* terms, 6 stored *Drugs and Chemical Substances* entities, 5 had *Proteins* entities and only 4 contained *Genes* terms.

When it comes to the size of the corpus, the median of the number of entities between 8 corpora (the other 2 remaining are not counted because we could not find their number) is 45,661 entities. The biggest one contains 190,679 entities and the smallest 1066 entities.

We also looked for the formats in which their annotations were published. Among the 10 corpora, 3 of them have their annotations in the brat format, 3 created their own format and the rest did not specify what was the format. Most of these last what specified was the type of file in which they publish the annotations, for example in a XML file.

Finally, it was analysed which were the sources and databases from which the authors obtained the text input to annotate the corpora. The sources most employed were Pubmed and MEDLINE, used by 6 out of 10 corpora. The rest of the corpora used resources less known and more specific such as clinical repositories from Universities and Hospitals.

3. Creation process

9 of the 10 corpora were manually annotated, and the last remaining was the result of a web crawling process (indexing data on web pages by employing a program or automated script). From the manual ones, the median of the number of total annotators was five annotators, being the largest one with 25 annotators and the smallest 3 people. In all the corpora, at least two people had to annotate the same text to compare the annotations.

We also searched if there was another type of resource employed to construct the corpus. From the 10 corpora, 8 of them employed some terminologies and ontologies to establish the entities and relations they wanted to annotate. The most employed ones are the United Medical Language System (UMLS) terminology and MeSH ([29](#)) vocabulary.

When it comes to the annotation process, 7 of the 10 corpora employed an annotation guideline. Additionally, the most employed annotation tool is BRAT rapid annotation tool, used by 4 of corpora; from the remaining, 2 of them employed Knowtator, and the rest either is not specified, or they used one of their own creation.

To measure the validation of their annotations, 6 of the 10 corpora used the F-measure to use it as a type of Inter-Annotator Agreement metric. This is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. In order to calculate this, for each annotation it is needed an annotation reference to

compare. Some of the authors used one annotator as the reference, and others used annotations obtained using a Name-Entity Recognition model. The corpora remaining either haven't used a metric to validate their annotations or haven't specified.

4. Availability

Finally, we searched for the availability in the web for the following resources for each corpus:

- *Code*: Only 4 articles published the code used for the whole project.
- *Data*: We searched for the input data used to annotate. Again, 4 corpora published this data, another 1 only published 70% of it and the remaining did not submit any.
- *Corpus' annotations*: 6 of the 10 corpora published openly the annotations of the corpus. We also found some cases in which inside the article it is specified a URL to the annotations, but when we tried to access it, it gave us an error.
- *Annotation guidelines*: These were available for 6 corpora; the rest remaining did not publish it or did not have one.
- *Corpus' licence*: Only 5 articles specified the licence of their corpus. Among the 5 articles, 4 of them had a Creative Commons licence (1 of them Creative Commons Attribution 3.0, 1 with Creative Commons BY 4.0, and 2 with Creative Commons Non-Commercial Attribution (CC-BY-NC-A) 4.0). The remaining one had a GNU Lesser General Public Licence (LGPL).

5.1.5. Conclusions

The conduct of this review confirms that the proportion of English biomedical corpora is still much larger than the number of Spanish biomedical corpora. Most of the corpora analysed contain more medical entities (such as Disease and Drugs) than other types like molecular entities (such as Protein or Gene). The output format most employed is the brat format, which is related with the fact that the annotation tool most used by the researchers is BRAT rapid annotation tool. This is a free and open tool which allows the annotation of entities and relations, and the brat format is a simple Tab-Separated Values (TSV) file which makes it easy to handle. Annotated corpora outnumber auto-annotated corpora, indicating a greater preference for the Gold Standard Corpus. Most of these employed two or three annotators label the same texts. To carry out this task, the creation of an annotation guideline is essential to improve the quality of the annotations. This is usually measured using the F-measure metric; however, it has the disadvantage that it needs an annotation reference to calculate it.

Finally, the 60% of the corpora claim to have the annotations published, however, only the 40% of them indicate what licence they have. Most of them neither published the data input and code, which prevents promoting reproducible science.

5.2. Spanish Biomedical Corpus

After applying the workflow and resources established in the Materials and Methods section, we ended up with a total number of 54 annotation files in brat format, 18 per annotator.

Statistics of the corpus

As a result, this corpus contains a total number of **324 entities** and **170 relations** annotated. Below, in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5** we can see the numbers of entities and relations annotated per category. Looking at the number of the entities (**Figure 4**), it is quite clear that the category more annotated is *Enfermedad (Disease)* with more than 100 terms labelled within that group which represents 32% of the total. Following there is *Signo (Clinic Sign)* with more than 80 entities, that is, 27% of the total number of entities. On the opposite, the categories with the smallest number of terms were *Lípido (Lipid)* with 2 terms, and *Glúcido (Carbohydrates)* with 3 terms annotated. There wasn't any term annotated within the category *Gen (Gene)*. Since the text inputs used are clinical reports, it is consistent that the most frequent entities belong to the medicine field while the least frequent belong to a more molecular biology area. From all the terms annotated from all the files, the most frequent is "TCA" labelled as *Sigla*.

Figure 4. Representation of the number of entities per category. Above each bar is labeled the exact number of entities.

When it comes to the semantic relations annotated (**Figure 5**), we can see that there is a clear decompensation in the number of each category. The relation *Implicado en* (*Involved in*) represents 69% of the total relations annotated, being the second most frequent the relation *Cura* (*It treats*) with a 14%. Additionally, there were three groups of relations that were not annotated at all: *Activa* (*Activates*), *Inhibe* (*Inhibits*) and *Previene* (*Prevents*). Looking at all the relations annotated, we see that the kind of relation most frequent is *[Proteína] - Implicado en → [Enfermedad]*.

Figure 5. Representation of the number of relations per category. Above each bar is labeled the exact number of relations.

5.3. Evaluation of the annotations

As it was explained in the section 3.4 of Materials and Methods, the Fleiss' Kappa metric was calculated to measure the agreement between the annotators. In **Figure 6** and **Figure 7**, we can see the distribution of the Fleiss' Kappa value between the eighteen files for the entities and for the relations.

In the case of the entities (**Figure 6**), we can see that the vast majority of the annotated files obtained a Fleiss' Kappa value between 0.1 and 0.3. On one hand, there is one file in which there wasn't any agreement and on the other hand, there is one file that almost achieves a 0.5 value. Taking a look at the literature (30), we can see that values of Fleiss' Kappa between 0.1 and 0.5 indicate a fair/moderate agreement of the annotators.

Number of file per Fleiss' Kappa of annotated entities

Figure 6. Distribution of number of annotated files (axis y) by value of Fleiss' Kappa (axis x) for entities annotated.

Additionally, annotators show when it comes to the semantic relations annotated (*Figure 7*) really low values of Fleiss' Kappa. All the annotated files, except for one, have obtained a value less than zero, which means that there has been almost no agreement between the annotators. As a result, by calculating the median of the values for all the eighteen files, this corpus got a Fleiss' Kappa of **0.21 for entities** and **-0.37 for semantic relations**. These values represent that the agreement between the annotators is poor, especially in the semantic relations. Since the annotators have the same biomedical background, we could think that the indications for the annotation given by the annotation guideline are not accurate enough.

Figure 7. Distribution of number of annotated files (axis y) by value of Fleiss' Kappa (axis x) for semantic relations annotated.

The 54 files with the annotations in brat format (18 per annotator), the annotation guideline, the TextAE usage guideline and the data input can be found at the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6699943>. They are published with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence.

6. Discussion

In this project we have done a systematic review of Spanish and English biomedical annotated corpora from whose results we have designed a work environment with a serie of tools and resources that allow us to carry out the creation of a preliminary version of a corpus in Spanish annotated with biomedical entities and with their semantic relationships.

As a result of the systematic review, we identified 28 comparison features from 10 different corpora, 9 of them English and 1 Spanish. We saw that the final dataset is quite small and that it lacks English corpora of great importance such as the GENIA corpus or the NCBI disease. There is only one Spanish corpus in the review and some important ones, such as the

IxaMedGS, are missing on this review (10). The reason behind this is probably that the Inclusion-Exclusion filtering step carried out is really restricted, since we filtered by searching some specific words in their title. An approach that could have been done to avoid this problem is by filtering by those words in the abstracts.

We have found only three reviews of annotated corpora with biomedical entities. Neves M. (13) carried out a review of thirty-six biological corpora but only focusing on the different types of semantic entities they contained. Cohen, K.B et al (14) reviewed six biomedical English corpora by seeking which are the design features that characterise the widely used and the infrequently used ones. Finally, AlShuweih, M. et al (8) performed a review of three biomedical corpora, one Spanish, one Italian and one Chinese from which they analysed the creation motivation, the methodology, the data collection, and results. This last review is the closest to the one we performed, since it indicates the databases and criteria employed to collect the final dataset of corpora, and that it also contains corpora from other languages than in English. In our review, not only a major number of corpora are studied, but also a higher number of features are extracted, for example the availability section.

The results of this systematic review were employed to design a work environment of tools and resources in order to annotate a Spanish corpus with biomedical entities and relations. Then, these resources were applied to a sample of eighteen clinical reports from the SPACC corpus. Finally, there were identified **324 biomedical entities** and **170 semantic relations**. Regarding the biomedical entities, in **Figure 5A** we can see that an imbalance event occurs between the different groups of entities. A proportion of 67% belong to the classes “*Enfermedad*”, “*Síntoma*” and “*Signo*”. This was already predicted to happen since the text input we have used are clinical reports. Therefore, it is consistent that the most frequent entities are those of a more clinical scope and that the more molecular scope entities are in less proportion. Additionally, since we only employ a small number of the clinical cases, the probability of finding molecular entities decreases. However, it is in the annotated semantic relations where we find a much more pronounced imbalance. In **Figure 5B** we can see that the relation “*Implicado en*” outnumbers the rest of the relations by far. Looking at the annotation files in detail and analysing the comments that the annotators provided us, we realised that the way in which the relations are detailed in the annotation guide led them to understand that the guidelines of the subject entities and the object entities between relationships (see **Table 2**) served as a suggestion and not as an obligation. This could explain

why the Fleiss' Kappa values of the ratios (see **Figure 6B**) are so low. Since the annotators did not have strict annotation guidelines, there is a great heterogeneity between the annotations.

The values of Fleiss' Kappa of the annotations are for the **entities 0.21** and **-0.37 for the relations**. Apart from the fact that the annotation guide was not restrictive and clarifying enough, we have also found other possible causes of these low values. To calculate this metric, we established that to consider an agreement between the annotators, the entity not only had to be equal in the label level, but also it had to be the same as the span level. For example, if annotator A has annotated “*atrofia parenquimatosa*” (in English “parenchymal atrophy”) as “*Signo*” and annotator B has annotated “*atrofia parenquimatosa severa*” (in English “severe parenchymal atrophy”) also as “*Signo*”, our method would consider these different entities even though they only differentiate in one adjective. For future work, it may be interesting to search for other approaches that consider this type of relaxed agreement. In other corpora annotated with biomedical entities, the F-measure measure has been used as another possible annotation validation metric (9, 31, 32, 33, 34). However, to do so, it is needed to have annotations that act like that gold standard reference. What the authors usually do is to consider the annotations of an annotator as the reference (9), however we consider that then the corpus would be biased to the criteria of that annotator, and therefore we decided to continue to employ the Fleiss' Kappa as the validation metric.

We have found two main corpora annotated in Spanish with biomedical entities that have similarities with the work we have done. Campillos-Llanos, L., Valverde-Mateos, A., Capllonch-Carrión, A. et al. (9) created the Clinical Trials for Evidence-Based Medicine in Spanish (CT-EBM-SP) corpus, consisting in 1200 texts about clinical trials annotated with entities from four semantic groups from the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) (35), pathologies (DISO), anatomic entities (ANAT), biochemical or pharmacological substances (CHEM) and diagnostic or therapeutic procedures and lab tests (PROC). The main differences between this project and ours are: 1) They only a 10% of their texts is labelled by two annotators; 2) They look for a more general annotation of the words by using only the four groups of entities Anatomy, Pharmacological and chemical substances, Pathologies (DISO), and lab tests, diagnostic or therapeutic procedures, while we decided to approach for more specific biomedical entities; and 3) They did not annotated semantic relations. The second corpus is the one carried out by Baez Benavides, Pablo et al (36) consisting of 5,000

clinical referrals annotated with 10 types of medical entities. They also published the annotations in brat format in Zenodo. However, they only annotated one kind of semantic relation. These two corpus mentioned have in common that for the creation of their annotations they carried out a training and testing phase of the annotators and a final annotation phase. Our project is what we consider this testing phase, in which from a small sample of a large collection of texts, we have carried out the annotations to test and analyse what has to be improved from the resources of the workflow we created.

7. Conclusions

Considering the established objectives that we had established at the beginning, in this project we have achieved:

- The identification of the main standards and methodology employed in the state of art in English and Spanish biomedical corpus. The review performed allowed us to recognize which are the main resources employed by most researchers in this kind of process. However, it is necessary to carry out an improvement in the compilation of the corpora since we identified that it lacks corpora of great importance.
- Design an environmental work that allows to easily annotate Spanish clinical text with eleven types of biomedical entities and eight types of semantic relations and apply it to a small sample of clinical reports. Nevertheless, the annotation guideline needs to be modified to obtain more homogeneity between the annotators.

For future work, we are planning to modify the types of entities and semantic relations to annotate. It is necessary to establish a hierarchy between the entity classes in order to somewhat mitigate the imbalance between the classes. Additionally, it will be added new classes such as “*Patógeno*” (*Pathogen* in English) and its subclasses “*Virus*”, “*Bacteria*”, “*Hongos*” and “*Protozoo*” (*Virus*, *Bacteria*, *Fungus* and *Protozoan* respectively). Regarding the semantic relations, the relation “*Implicado en*” will be substituted by more specific relations. The number of possible subject and object entities between relations would be decreased to further restrict the annotators and promote more homogeneity.

Once these changes in the annotation guideline are done, the whole process will be applied to the 1000 clinical reports of SPACCC to check how this workflow results when it is applied to a bigger input. The final annotated corpus should be employed to train a supervised machine learning model and check if this dataset created improves its performance.

8. References

1. Blaschke, C., Hirschman, L., & Valencia, A. (2002). Information extraction in molecular biology. *Briefings in bioinformatics*, 3(2), 154–165. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/3.2.154>
2. Meystre, S. M., Savova, G. K., Kipper-Schuler, K. C., & Hurdle, J. F. (2008). Extracting information from textual documents in the electronic health record: a review of recent research. *Yearbook of medical informatics*, 128–144.
3. Haerian, K., Varn, D., Vaidya, S., Ena, L., Chase, H.S. and Friedman, C. (2012), Detection of Pharmacovigilance-Related Adverse Events Using Electronic Health Records and Automated Methods. *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 92: 228-234. <https://doi.org/10.1038/clpt.2012.54>
4. Wynne, M (editor). (2005). *Developing Linguistic Corpora: a Guide to Good Practice*. Oxford: Oxbow Books. Available online from <http://ota.ox.ac.uk/documents/creating/dlc/>
5. Kim, J. D., Ohta, T., Tateisi, Y., & Tsujii, J. (2003). GENIA corpus--semantically annotated corpus for bio-textmining. *Bioinformatics (Oxford, England)*, 19 Suppl 1, i180–i182. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btg1023>
6. Roberts, A., Gaizauskas, R., Hepple, M., Demetriou, G., Guo, Y., Roberts, I., & Setzer, A. (2009). Building a semantically annotated corpus of clinical texts. *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 42(5), 950–966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2008.12.013>
7. Doğan, R. I., Leaman, R., & Lu, Z. (2014). NCBI disease corpus: a resource for disease name recognition and concept normalization. *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 47, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2013.12.006>
8. AlShuweih, M., Salloum, S.A., Shaalan, K. (2021). Biomedical Corpora and Natural Language Processing on Clinical Text in Languages Other Than English: A Systematic Review. In: Al-Emran, M., Shaalan, K., Hassanien, A. (eds) *Recent Advances in Intelligent Systems and Smart Applications*. Studies in Systems,

Decision and Control, vol 295. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-47411-9_27

9. Campillos-Llanos, L., Valverde-Mateos, A., Capllonch-Carrión, A. et al. (2021). A clinical trials corpus annotated with UMLS entities to enhance the access to evidence-based medicine. *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak* 21, 69 .
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-021-01395-z>
10. Oronoz, M., Gojenola, K., Pérez, A., de Ilarraza, A. D., & Casillas, A. (2015). On the creation of a clinical gold standard corpus in Spanish: Mining adverse drug reactions. *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 56, 318–332.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2015.06.016>
11. Viviana Cotik, Darío Filippo, Roland Roller, Hans Uszkoreit, and Feiyu Xu. (2017). Annotation of Entities and Relations in Spanish Radiology Reports. In *Proceedings of the International Conference Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing, RANLP 2017*, pages 177–184, Varna, Bulgaria. INCOMA Ltd.
http://dx.doi.org/10.26615/978-954-452-049-6_025
12. Kitchenham, B. A. & Charters, S. (2007). *Guidelines for performing Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering (EBSE 2007-001)*. Keele University and Durham University Joint Report
13. Neves M. (2014). An analysis on the entity annotations in biological corpora. *F1000Research*, 3, 96. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.3216.1>
14. CK. Bretonnel Cohen, Lynne Fox, Philip V. Ogren, and Lawrence Hunter. (2005). *Corpus Design for Biomedical Natural Language Processing*. In *Proceedings of the ACL-ISMB Workshop on Linking Biological Literature, Ontologies and Databases: Mining Biological Semantics*, pages 38–45, Detroit. Association for Computational Linguistics.
15. Web of Science <https://www.recursoscientificos.fecyt.es/>
16. Scopus <https://www.recursoscientificos.fecyt.es/>
17. Pubmed [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Library of Medicine (US), National Center for Biotechnology Information. Available from:
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>
18. Ander Intxaurreondo. (2018). SPACCC (2019-02-01) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2560316>

19. Pontus Stenetorp, Sampo Pyysalo, Goran Topić, Tomoko Ohta, Sophia Ananiadou and Jun'ichi Tsujii (2012). brat: a Web-based Tool for NLP-Assisted Text Annotation. In Proceedings of the Demonstrations Session at EACL 2012.
20. Jin-Dong Kim, Yue Wang, Shigeru Nakajima and Nakashima Masahiro. <https://textae.pubannotation.org/>
21. Pustejovsky, J., Castaño, J., Cochran, B., Kotecki, M., & Morrell, M. (2001). Automatic extraction of acronym-meaning pairs from MEDLINE databases. *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 84(Pt 1), 371–375
22. McCray, A. T., & Nelson, S. J. (1995). The representation of meaning in the UMLS. *Methods of information in medicine*, 34(1-2), 193–201
23. Real Academia Nacional de Medicina de España (2012). Diccionario de Términos Médicos. Versión electrónica: <http://dtme.ranm.es/index.aspx>
24. Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales. Vocabulario Científico y Técnico de la Real Academia de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales (VCTRAC). Versión digital: https://vctrac.es/index.php?title=P%C3%A1gina_principal
25. Fleiss, Joseph L. (1971). Measuring nominal scale agreement among many raters.. *Psychological Bulletin*, 76(5), 378–382. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/h0031619>
26. Seabold, S., & Perktold, J. (2010). statsmodels: Econometric and statistical modeling with python. In 9th Python in Science Conference.
27. European Organization For Nuclear Research, & OpenAIRE. (2013). Zenodo. doi:10.25495/7GXX-RD71
28. Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
29. Lipscomb C. E. (2000). Medical Subject Headings (MeSH). *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association*, 88(3), 265–266.
30. Viera, A. J., & Garrett, J. M. (2005). Understanding interobserver agreement: the kappa statistic. *Family medicine*, 37(5), 360–363.
31. Deleger, L., Li, Q., Lingren, T., Kaiser, M., Molnar, K., Stoutenborough, L., Kouril, M., Marsolo, K., & Solti, I. (2012). Building gold standard corpora for medical natural language processing tasks. *AMIA ... Annual Symposium proceedings. AMIA Symposium*, 2012, 144–153.

32. Legrand, J., Gogdemir, R., Bousquet, C. et al. (2020). PGxCorpus, a manually annotated corpus for pharmacogenomics. *Sci Data* 7, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0342-9>
33. Philip Ogren, Guergana Savova, and Christopher Chute. (2008). Constructing Evaluation Corpora for Automated Clinical Named Entity Recognition. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'08)*, Marrakech, Morocco. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).
34. Hripcsak, G., & Rothschild, A. S. (2005). Agreement, the f-measure, and reliability in information retrieval. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association : JAMIA*, 12(3), 296–298. <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.M1733>
35. Bodenreider O. (2004). The Unified Medical Language System (UMLS): integrating biomedical terminology. *Nucleic acids research*, 32(Database issue), D267–D270. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh061>
36. Pablo Báez, Felipe Bravo-Marquez, Jocelyn Dunstan, Matías Rojas, and Fabián Villena. (2022). Automatic Extraction of Nested Entities in Clinical Referrals in Spanish. *ACM Trans. Comput. Healthcare* 3, 3, Article 28 (July 2022), 22 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3498324>

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Below is the table with the characteristics and results obtained after performing a systematic review of the literature in corpus annotated with biomedical entities in English and Spanish. It is divided in four sections:

- 1) **Article information**
- 2) **Corpus information**
- 3) **Creation process**
- 4) **Availability**

	INFORMATION ARTICLE					
Articles' Title	Year of publication	Article's DOI	Source of publication	Name of the source of publication	Q index of the source of publication	What is the article's availability?
NERO: a biomedical named-entity (recognition) ontology with a large, annotated corpus reveals meaningful associations through text embedding	2021	10.1038/s41540-021-00200-x	Journal	npj Systems Biology and Applications	Q1	Open Access
A clinical trials corpus annotated with UML S entities to enhance the access to evidence-based medicine	2021	10.1186/s12911-021-01395-z	Journal	BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making	Q2	Open Access
Concept annotation in the CRAFT corpus	2012	10.1186/1471-2105-13-161	Journal	BMC Bioinformatics	Q1	Open Access
A multilingual gold-standard corpus for biomedical concept recognition: The Mantra GSC	2015	10.1093/jamia/ocv037	Journal	Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association	Q1	Open Access
Building a semantically annotated corpus of clinical texts	2009	10.1016/j.jbi.2008.12.013 *	Journal	Journal of Biomedical Informatics	Q1	Open Access
Biointer: A corpus for information extraction in the biomedical domain	2007	10.1186/1471-2105-8-50	Journal	BMC Bioinformatics	Q1	Open Access
GNI Corpus Version 1.0: Annotated Full-Text Corpus of Genomics & Informatics to Support Biomedical Information Extraction	2018	10.5808/GI.2018.16.3.75	Journal	Genomics & Informatics	NF	Open Access
Building an OMOP common data model-compliant annotated corpus for COVID-19 clinical trials	2021	10.1016/j.jbi.2021.103790	Journal	J Biomed Inform	Q1	Open Access
Extracting COVID-19 diagnoses and symptoms from clinical text: A new annotated corpus and neural event extraction framework	2021	10.1016/j.jbi.2021.103761	Journal	J Biomed Inform	Q1	Open Access
BRONCO: Biomedical entity Relation Oncology Corpus for extracting gene-variant-disease-drug relations	2016	10.1093/database/baw043	Journal	Database	Q1	Open Access
F = False						
T = True						
NF = Not found						
DA = Don't apply						

	RESOURCE AVAILABILITY				
Articles' Title	Is the code available?	Is the data available?	Is the corpus available?	Are the annotation guidelines available?	What license does the corpus have?
NERO : a biomedical named-entity (recognition) ontology with a large, annotated corpus reveals meaningful associations through text embedding	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NF
A clinical trials corpus annotated with UMLS entities to enhance the access to evidence-based medicine	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Creative Commons Non-Commercial Attribution (CC-BY-NC-A) 4.0
Concept annotation in the CRAFT corpus	Yes	Only the 70%	Yes	Yes	Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 license (CC BY)
A multilingual gold-standard corpus for biomedical concept recognition: The Mantra GSC	NF	Yes	Yes	Yes	Creative Commons BY 4.0 license
Building a semantically annotated corpus of clinical texts	NF	NF	No	No	NF
BioInfer: A corpus for information extraction in the biomedical domain	NF	NF	NF	No	GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL)
GNI Corpus Version 1.0: Annotated Full-Text Corpus of Genomics & Informatics to Support Biomedical Information Extraction	Yes	No	Yes	DA	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International
Building an OMP common data model-compliant annotated corpus for COVID-19 clinical trials	NF	Yes	Yes	NF	NF
Extracting COVID-19 diagnoses and symptoms from clinical text: A new annotated corpus and neural event extraction framework	NF	NF	NF	Yes	NF
BRONCO: Biomedical entity Relation Oncology Corpus for extracting gene-variant-disease-drug relations	No	No	No	Yes	NF
F = False					
T = True					
NF = Not found					
DA = Don't apply					